

REFLECTIVE WRITING AS EMPLOYABILITY SKILL OF BUSINESS STUDENTS

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The objective to implement reflective writing in Business degree programs is to upgrade students' employability skills since most high education institutions have gaps in smooth transition of graduates from university level to workplace. The major challenge in preparing students for job entry requirements is divergencies between graduates' attained knowledge and skills and employers' expectations. In other words, some universities are unable to provide that knowledge and skills demanded in current job market. Similar situation is happening in Business oriented universities. The studies show that present managers require a set of employability skills such as critical thinking, communication skills, problem-solving, decision-making, adaptability, stress tolerance, reflectivity and others from university graduates. However, as different researches findings demonstrate, most learners are not well-prepared to enroll into job and progress in it. As a result, many countries including Uzbekistan, have been facing unemployment issues among university graduates. To improve the situation, employability skills should be fully implemented into high educational institutions' curriculum and learners should be engaged in real world experiences. This can be achieved through integrating reflective writing into lessons so that students can develop their skills, particularly critical thinking skills. Several studies indicate positive outcomes of improving critical thinking skills via reflective writing teaching strategy.

One of the main purposes for developing Business students' reflective writing skills is current employability requirements. In fact, the set of skills and characteristics sought by employers is referred as employability skills. As Mainga et al. (2022) define, employability of university graduates includes relevant skills and professional features that students will need to pursue their careers, develop in their

jobs, if needed, shift to another job and advance in their careers. The survey conducted by the Confederation of British Industry in 2011, as cited by Mainga et al. (2022), explain that graduate employability is a collection of skills and knowledge, abilities and characteristics that enable students to find a job, succeed in their careers and turn into “critical and reflective life-long learners” who can adapt within their careers for the sake of themselves, companies, society and economy. Accordingly, a number of universities have introduced employability as their mission alongside with teaching, research and community service (Campbell et al. 2019, as cited by Mainga et al. 2022). Indeed, the most essential skills that employers look for in potential candidates are adaptability, critical thinking, spoken and written communication skills, creative thinking, leadership, teamwork, problem solving, stress tolerance and others. Recent studies show that future employees should possess “self-awareness, persistence, social and cultural awareness, self-efficacy, reflectivity” as indispensable part of their professional profile (Mainga et al., 2022). Ajwad et al. (2014) interpret the survey aimed for identifying the list of skills required from job candidates by Uzbek employers in 2013. The current survey data show that Uzbek recruiters were seeking the candidates who had both cognitive and non-cognitive skills. Cognitive skills included critical thinking, problem-solving, numeracy skills and spoken performance ability, whereas non-cognitive skills comprised growth mindset, decision making, adaptability and persistency.

In fact, employers do not always meet the candidates who possess those required employability skills. More often managers express their dissatisfactions with poor or underdeveloped skills that university graduates have. The research made by Ajwad et al. demonstrate Uzbek employers` concerns regarding hiring right candidates with necessary skills. As the study findings reveal, 49% of Uzbek managers considered that there was significant undersupply in specialists with higher education degree (Ajwad et al., 2014). As Mainga et al. (2022) highlight, several studies were made to investigate to what extent university graduates` acquired skills and knowledge complement with organizations` job recruitment requirements in countries like Great Britain, Portugal, Germany, the USA, Canada, India, Vietnam, China, South Africa,

Nigeria and others. The findings revealed a marked divergence between expectations and reality. Bouanani (2015) points out that one of the universities in Morocco, where the research was conducted, also experienced mismatch between learning outcomes of university degree programs and skills that university graduates were able to attain. In fact, the research shows that most graduates of this university could not master writing, reading and particularly thinking skills set in learning objectives by the time they graduated.

Certainly, significant number of university graduates have been facing unemployment issues due to above-mentioned discrepancies between their knowledge and organizations` job entry requirements. For instance, around 30% of business graduates in Australia were without jobs four months later after their graduation in 2015 (Graduate Careers Australia, 2015 as cited by Mainga et al., 2022). As Minocha et al. (2018) as cited by Mainga et al. (2022) point out, approximately 58% of graduates were employed in unqualified and non-graduate professions in Great Britain. According to the publication made by Aliyeva on daryo.uz (2024), Uzbekistan experienced 6.8% unemployment rate in 2023. For the time being, there are 2 million 400 thousand unemployed people in Uzbekistan (Aliyeva, 2024). Uzbekistan`s Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction as cited by Aliyeva (2024) indicates skill mismatch as one of the key reasons of unemployment in Uzbekistan, in addition to insufficiencies in investments and divergencies in employment opportunities among regions in the country.

Several studies were made to identify the connectedness between reflective writing and critical thinking. As Bouanani (2015) suggest in her research, metacognitive processes that happen in critical thinking and reflective writing blend with each other. The current research proves that reflective writing alongside with other teaching strategies develops students` critical thinking skills specialized in Finance, Marketing and Entrepreneurship (Bouanani, 2015). Almost four decades ago in 1987, researchers as Schon and Brookfield and later Mezirow in 1990, proposed the idea of reflective thinking, which evolved from the person as a thinker. According to this idea, a thinker has to recognize, analyze, estimate his/her thoughts and

viewpoints. The current process can result in revisiting personal past experiences and background knowledge on the given issue (Bouanani, 2015). What is essential, students can consider and comprehend “how and why they think the way they do”, since by revisiting past experiences they become involved in metacognitive process. With the help of metacognitive process, learners can recognize their values, beliefs and attitudes and deal with reflective thinking in any context. This can serve as a connecting bridge between what students already know and what they study and can promote active learning. By integrating writing into thinking process, teachers can ensure improvement in students` thinking, learning and comprehension stages (Bouanani, 2015). If learners understand well the subject of what they write, their writing can be useful for them. Bouanani (2015) recommends to refer to real world context while using reflection as a teaching method because real-life cases can perfectly formulate critical thinking skills. Craft (2005), Kennison (2006) and Moon (2008) as cited by Bouanani (2015) believe that real-life situations can encourage critical thinking ability, self-understanding resulting in becoming self-assured and confident learner.

To conclude, contemporary organizations seek candidates with well-developed employability skills. This requires swift attention and right decisions from universities to integrate necessary skills into the curriculum and set appropriate learning outcomes. As it has been suggested, using reflective writing as a teaching instrument in Business degree programs can significantly enhance students` critical thinking skills. By this, universities can offer graduates with well-developed critical thinking skills and assist students to meet job entry requirements. Consequently, graduates can pursue their desired careers by helping the organizations to achieve their common goals.

Reference list:

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